

Today's cutting-edge artificial intelligence (AI) techniques are making their way into the edge devices of tomorrow. Europe has the potential to be a leader in low-power, high-performance edge systems that combine the best of all AI approaches and serve the sectors that are most important to Europe.

AI for better integration between the physical and the cyber world: Embedded AI

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Artificial intelligence allows computer systems to better interact with the physical world, either by interpreting (sequences of) images, sound, signals etc, or by generating more realistic audio, speech or video signals. This is the main ingredient in the new generation of cyber-physical systems (CPS) that, in turn, will be key for the “next web”, ambient intelligence, the physical web, etc. For reasons of privacy, efficiency, etc., more and more of this processing will be run on edge devices, thanks to algorithm improvements and better hardware performance. Often, the first layers are made by deep neural network (DNN) systems, while the higher levels are often performed by more “traditional” algorithmic approaches.

Key insights

- The interfaces between the physical world and computing systems are key for the next generation of systems, such as the “next web”, ambient intelligence, autonomous systems, etc.
- For reasons of privacy, latency and energy efficiency, it is often desirable for computations to be performed locally, “at the edge”.
- Both DNN and more algorithmic approaches (where knowledge is explicitly introduced into the system) should be used.
- Voice interfaces are becoming more and more important for consumer systems (both recognition and synthesis) as natural means of interaction.
- Impressive new levels of performance will be achieved thanks to the fusion of different modalities and continuous signals, e.g. a sequence of images instead of a single image.
- Europe has the potential to be leader in this kind of system, but Chinese and American companies are already in the race, and are developing integrated circuits (ICs) for edge applications.

Key recommendations

- Europe should aim to retain its leading position in the field of low-power, local processing, using both DNN and algorithmic approaches for the edge use cases prevalent in Europe.
- Development environments and tools should be developed in order to translate/map complex DNN into embedded chips (using pruning, quantization, etc...)
- The diversity of European languages is an opportunity to develop more efficient integrated solutions suitable to the European market. These should be in accordance with European requirements and ethical standards.
- Europe should be at the forefront of making accelerators using state-of-the-art AI algorithms.
- Europe has good levels of knowledge and education relating to technologies required to make edge AI devices, but concretization into products is still lacking.

Artificial intelligence allows computers to interact better with the world and humans

Deep learning provided breakthroughs as a way of analysing unstructured data such as images and sound, as well as allowing an efficient interface between computers and the world, facilitating cyber-physical applications. This has really opened up possibilities for new solutions and business propositions, like self-driving cars, personal assistants and so on. Image and sequence analysis allow autonomous vehicles to check their surrounding and to take appropriate decisions. Most of the time, several modalities (images, Lidar data, ultrasonic data) can be used and merged to get a better analysis. The fusion of different modalities is an important topic for AI at the edge.

Personal assistants

In addition to image classification, progress in AI, particularly deep learning, has been made very visible by advances in voice recognition, which paved the way for the emergence of voice-activated personal assistants like Siri from Apple, Google Assistant, Alexa from Amazon, Cortana from Microsoft, Bixbi from Samsung, Duer from Baidu, Viv, etc. Indeed, for most people today the visible part of AI is embodied by these personal assistants. Voice is a natural way of communicating for humans, and, if the AI works well, it is also a way for people who are not very familiar with computers or keyboards to access digital technologies.

Improvements in the accuracy of recognition have also triggered the development of specific accelerator hardware (in the case of Google), as explained in this blog post from 2017 [2]:

“The need for TPUs really emerged about six years ago, when we started using computationally expensive deep learning models in more and more places throughout our products. The computational expense of using these models had us worried. If we considered a scenario where people use Google voice search for just three minutes a day and we ran deep neural nets for our speech recognition system on the processing units we were using, we would have had to double the number of Google data centers.”

Figure 1: Deep MANTA, a neural network algorithm to perform advanced and efficient real-time analysis of video streams for autonomous vehicle perception systems (from CEA) [1]

Personal assistants first appeared in mobile phones (Google Assistant for Android, and Siri for Apple). They proved useful for some activities, like dictating and reading text messages and emails in cars, but the touchscreen interface was still more convenient for most applications. It was only when they were incorporated into a

speaker for use in the home that they really found their niche.

The market for virtual assistants

First introduced by Amazon in its Echo device in November 2014, the company's Alexa assistant is a market leader in terms of smart speaker sales. (Google Assistant

Figure 2: Proportion of people having answered to the pool who own a smart speaker (from [3])

“Personable or not, intelligent voice agents are poised to alter the nature of computing as we know it.

Since the dawn of the PC, humans have been forced to learn an arcane, unnatural language. But in a voice-first world, mediated by artificial intelligence and machine learning ... the next 50 years will see computers learning to be more like us.” [4]

and Siri from Apple have also a very large number of instances because they are embedded in smartphones, but for the purposes of the current discussion we will focus on the specific embodiment of assistants into dedicated devices such as smart speakers).

According to Statista, Alexa can control more than 100,000 different smart home devices, and in 2019 Amazon announced that more than 100 million devices with Alexa on board had been sold. According to Voicebot.ai, there are now over 80,000 Alexa “skills” – what Amazon calls its voice apps – in the US alone and hundreds of thousands of developers in over 180 countries working on Alexa. Skills are small programs or apps developed by independent developers that run on the cloud and bring new capabilities to the Alexa personal assistant. However, there has apparently been a decline in the global growth rate of Alexa skills, which Voicebot has linked to waning developer enthusiasm for the platform [6] and a difficult economic model because most of them are free.

Google followed Amazon in 2016 with its Google Home speaker, which is rapidly growing in the market. Apple was next, introducing its HomePod embedding Siri in 2018.

Ecosystems are being created around them, with more and more devices becoming interoperable and therefore able to be controlled by voice. The introduction of Matter (“a standard for home automation, royalty-free, ... [that] aims at achieving interoperability among smart home devices and internet of things (IoT) platforms from different providers” [8]) will enable interoperability between the different assistants’ ecosystems.

A digest of statistics concerning smart speakers can be found at [9]. In 2020, Voicebot published information about a survey that “found that 87.7 million U.S. adults were using smart speakers as of January 2020. This means the installed base of U.S. smart speaker users is up 32% over January 2019 and is 85% higher than January 2018”. The article recognizes, however, that these figures “show a slowing relative growth rate” [10].

Figure 3: Smart speaker market share (from [5])

Figure 4: Total Alexa skills by country (from [6])

Figure 5: From left to right: Google Home, Apple HomePod mini and Amazon Echo speakers. From [7]

Note that, in addition to smart speakers, voice-controlled assistants are used in a range of other smart-home devices, as noted in [11].

From these figures, even with the slow-down due to the COVID-19 period, it seems that the market for voice assistants is established. However, due to the large support teams and computing resources required, virtual assistants are struggling to generate a return on investment. Most of the applications developed by their supporting communities are free, and people are not really willing to pay for this commodity. As an example, the “Worldwide Digital” group in Amazon “lost \$3 billion in just the first quarter of 2022, with “the vast majority” of the losses blamed on Alexa” [14], “every plan to monetize Alexa has failed”, and buying by voice command, foreseen by Amazon as a key asset for increasing its business, was never really a success. This suggests that, despite its potential, the way to create a thriving business model for virtual assistants is still not clear.

The appeal of virtual assistants

As noted in previous editions of the HiPEAC Vision, home assistants have an attractive service offering. They show their full usefulness when connected to the IoT or smart devices such as lights and appliances, controlling them remotely. As well as providing basic functions of web interaction – such as delivering weather forecasts, traffic reports or the time, making to-do lists, setting alarms, and fetching information from Wikipedia – they provide an ideal interface for streaming music. They have also been replacing radio with their enhanced functionalities to respond to requests for a particular song, piece of music or podcast. Another use is controlling smart devices in the home (light, power plugs, etc).

Their appeal partly lies in their role as a constantly available “butler” who obeys orders, helps automate routine tasks and helps users organize their lives. With access to the internet and company data, voice assistants could also participate in meetings as required, contributing relevant information during the discussion.

Figure 6: Smart home and smart speaker users in the US in 2021, from [9]

Figure 7: US total in-car voice assistant users in 2022, from [9]

As an example, in 2018 Google announced its Duplex technology which could be used for real-world tasks. The technology was demonstrated reserving a table at a restaurant and booking a haircut without human intervention; it has since been integrated into Google Assistant [15]. However, the natural-sounding conversation gave rise to concerns that the voice assistant should identify itself as AI, and not let the human with whom it is interacting believing it is also a human.

Duplex has also been promoted as a way to help mitigate the frustration of calling companies’ automated response services,

waiting on hold on callers’ behalf, as well as screening calls [16]. This kind of application has prompted some commentators to suggest that, rather than being tailored to an individual, customer-facing AI could be used by companies to provide an “improved” service [17].

One reason for the growing acceptance of these assistants is that voice is a natural way for humans to interact. They provide a way for people unfamiliar with computers to access resources without having to know how to use a computer or a particular user interface. Current voice assistants will probably evolve towards being more

Figure 8: US mobile app users who would like voice interaction options, from [12]

Figure 9: Smart speakers – worldwide revenue. Source [13]

personal and customizable, offering multiple modalities in addition to voice recognition, such as gesture recognition and mood analysis, and evolving to understand and operate in a larger context.

Nonetheless, commercial voice assistants have also attracted criticism for being “spies”, recording everything that is said in a house. Concerns over privacy have apparently risen; according to [18], in 2020 “33% of U.S. adults cite[d] concerns about smart speakers recording what they are saying as a top reason for not purchasing the devices”. Technically, this is not accurate, and the

behaviour is not the same for all assistants. While devices are always “listening” for the “wake” (trigger) word, the processing of this word is normally done locally, on the device. The streaming of sound recorded to external servers only takes place when the “wake” word is detected.

Of course, false triggering can happen. Apparently, in the case of Google Assistant, samples around the supposed triggering word are sent to the server for verification. Some samples of interactions are also analysed by humans to improve the service, which has led to privacy and ethical

concerns [19]. More generally, given that the devices have the capacity to listen and record, they have the potential for unprecedented surveillance in the absence of robust protections for users. Some of these issues are explored further in the article on privacy in this HiPEAC Vision.

However, the progress in AI algorithms and the development of new accelerator chips will decrease the need for assistants to use off-site servers, and more and more of the voice processing will be done locally. Using open-source technology that can be inspected, running locally on edge devices, could alleviate users’ fears.

A European flavour of virtual assistant

It is unfortunate that Europe does not have a strong presence in this domain, at least on the business-to-consumer (B2C) side. Even the European start-ups which do exist in this field, such as Snips [20], are generally bought by non-European companies (Snips was acquired by Sonos, and allows Sonos to have their own assistant running locally in their smart speakers). It seems that voice is a very good human-to-machine interface, one which could be widely accepted if users could trust the systems (in terms of privacy, cybersecurity, and the absence of manipulation by corporate interests), so it should be of common interest to have a European flavour of this technology.

Collaborative work around open source could be a way to integrate the different technologies required to make a trustable vocal assistant. Professor Monica Lam’s group at Stanford University has demonstrated that it is feasible to develop innovative concepts for designing a virtual assistant [21]. With the collaboration of several open-source initiatives in this field (including European ones such as LinTO [22]) and databases of various languages (such as Common Voice [23]), a fully functional, efficient, ethical, inspectable, trustworthy virtual assistant technology platform could be developed. The plurality of languages, accents and dialects in Europe could be a driver to develop European databases, speech-to-text and text-to-speech technologies tuned for European needs.

It would also be important to investigate different business models to make sure this technology is sustainable, or to ensure that it has a societal impact [24] allowing people uneasy with digital technology to easily access it, so that it should be developed with European funding to be available to all Europeans.

Dedicated chips allow local processing

Voice technology is advanced enough to have part or even most of the voice processing done locally: voice-to-text software is efficient on computers (for example, there is a native dictation application on Mac computers) and companies like Snips promote local processing to help keep privacy intact. This might require more processing power, but voice assistants already embedded in loudspeakers have the processing power of a medium-range smartphone. The development of AI accelerators and the new improvements and compression of voice recognition models allow more and more local processing in the devices themselves, minimizing communication with the cloud.

“The AZ2 chip builds on the machine learning interface that premiered with the AZ1, which allowed Amazon devices to better recognize your voice, but has extended this capability to facial recognition as well. This comes with Amazon’s new focus on what it calls “Ambient Intelligence.” [25]

Amazon, Google and Apple are increasingly tending towards local processing for their AI, and they have all integrated hardware accelerators for deep learning into their devices. For example, Google Translate can now run locally on a smartphone.

Chinese and Taiwanese companies also sell chips designed for local voice processing, mainly for voice commands. The Amazon AZ line of chips were developed in collaboration with Mediatek. Chips from iFlytek [26] are also used for smart assistants in China [27].

Examples of other companies in this field include Unisound with its US516P6 chip and Espressif. Espressif Systems is a public multinational, fabless semiconduc-

Figure 10: Examples of chips able to carry out (simple) voice recognition locally

Figure 11: Espressif’s voice system, according to [30]

Figure 12: the new Jetson Orin nano from NVIDIA, from [34]

tor company established in 2008, with offices in China, the Czech Republic, India, Singapore and Brazil [28]. According to their Q1 2022 report, the company generated revenue of about €202 million in the first quarter of 2022, while the company employs around 520 people (as of June 2022).

The Espressif model is interesting because it heavily relies on open source for software development (and the company hires the most active GitHub contributors). Espressif is also moving to the RISC-V open-source instruction set architecture, one of the building blocks of open-source hardware, and supports open-source developments (e.g. CircuitPython). One particu-

	Jetson Orin Nano 4GB	Jetson Orin Nano 8GB
AI Performance	20 Sparse TOPs 10 Dense TOPs	40 Sparse TOPs 20 Dense TOPs
GPU	512-core NVIDIA Ampere Architecture GPU with 16 Tensor Cores	1024-core NVIDIA Ampere Architecture GPU with 32 Tensor Cores
GPU Max Frequency	625 MHz	
CPU	6-core Arm Cortex-A78AE v8.2 64-bit CPU 1.5 MB L2 + 4 MB L3	
CPU Max Frequency	1.5 GHz	
Memory	4GB 64-bit LPDDR5 34 GB/s	8GB 128-bit LPDDR5 68 GB/s
Storage	- (Supports external NVMe)	
Video Encode	1080p30 supported by 1-2 CPU cores	
Video Decode	1x 4K60 (H.265) 2x 4K30 (H.265) 5x 1080p60 (H.265) 11x 1080p30 (H.265)	
Camera	Up to 4 cameras (8 through virtual channels*) 8 lanes MIPI CSI-2 D-PHY 2.1 (up to 20 Gbps)	
PCIe	1 x4 + 3 x1 (PCIe Gen3, Root Port, & Endpoint)	
USB	3x USB 3.2 Gen2 (10 Gbps) 3x USB 2.0	
Networking	1x GbE	
Display	1x 4K30 multimode DisplayPort 1.2 (+MST)/e DisplayPort 1.4/HDMI 1.4*	
Other I/O	3x UART, 2x SPI, 2x I2S, 4x I2C, 1x CAN, DMIC and DSPK, PWM, GPIOs	
Power	5W - 10W	7W - 15W
Mechanical	69.6 mm x 45 mm 260-pin SO-DIMM connector	
Price	\$199 [†]	\$299 [†]

Table 1. Jetson Orin Nano series specification

Figure 13: The specifications of Jetson Orin Nano, from [34]

Figure 14: Peak performance vs. power scatterplot of publicly announced AI accelerators and processors, from [37]

larity of the company is that they provide a longevity commitment of their products up to 12 years. They provide a local voice command system, offering the repository on Github [29, 30].

Their multinet [31] system can understand up to 200 speech commands (Chinese and English). More details on the wake word approach can be seen in [32]. Their model shows that relying on open source can be valuable for a company. Their chips are qualified platforms for ACS, “Amazon Common Software (ACS) for Devices”, which, as Espressif notes, is “Amazon’s optimized software that simplifies the integration of various Amazon Device SDKs in connected products” [33].

NVIDIA is also present in the edge market: in September 2022 the company introduced its Jetson Orin Nano, which, according to [34], reaches processing power of up to 40 sparse TOPs (float8?) on less than 15 W of power and at a cost of US\$ 299 for the complete system. Medium size voice recognition models should be able to run in real-time on such hardware.

European companies are also present in this field of ASICs combining a processor and AI accelerators. Companies like GreenWaves [35], ST Microelectronics, Infineon and NXP [36] all have products on the market. In fact, the market seems to be very crowded, according to a survey [37] from September 2021.

Local processing is the key to success for most “ambient intelligence” systems

Ambient intelligence is coming back into prominence according to Amazon [38]; indeed, the company chose it as the topic of a recent keynote talk about the Alexa ecosystem [39]. The term ambient intelligence is quite old, having been used e.g. by Philips 20 years ago [40]. Artificial intelligence is becoming more and more present in edge devices, not only for voice assistants and image recognition but also for tasks that were only available in the cloud until recently. For the forthcoming “metaverse”, 3D face reconstruction can be made locally, see for example [41] which can achieve 150 frames per second

on a single central processing unit (CPU) thread. This kind of work will allow direct animation of avatars in real time on edge devices (currently it can operate on PCs) without requiring expansive graphics processing units (GPUs) or access to the cloud. However, it could also make it easier to create deep fakes in real time.

Even complex models, like those that can generate images from text description, can be now run on consumer laptops. For example, DiffusionBee [42] can run models of Stable Diffusion [43] locally to generate images.

According to Wikipedia, “the model of Stable Diffusion was trained using 256 Nvidia A100 GPUs on Amazon Web Services for a total of 150,000 GPU-hours, at a cost of \$600,000” [44]. It uses a “latent diffusion model, a variety of deep generative neural network developed by the CompVis group at LMU Munich”. Since it was released in the public domain, many developers have worked on it, making different ports and interfaces, and creating websites [45] to display the results of the algorithms. In inference (to generate new images), it runs in a few seconds on a MacBook with the M1 processor, showing that this kind of big model can be executed at the edge (not yet in embedded systems), leading to new potential usages.

AI at the edge: combining DNN and algorithm-driven approaches

As seen with voice systems, the overall approach to AI often involves a combination of DNN for phoneme detection, and more “traditional” approaches (or statistical) to determine the probability of the words. In autonomous vehicles, the detection and analysis of the environment is often performed by deep learning techniques, while data fusion can use other techniques (Bayesian, etc) and decisions are taken by rule-based or algorithm-driven approaches (although it should be noted that deep learning is also making progress in this domain).

Together, deep learning techniques and more traditional approaches (based on explicit knowledge) are a powerful combination that can lead to interesting results.

Figure 15: Results [41] allowing real-time animation of avatars at the edge

Figure 16: Image generated on a laptop with DiffusionBee (parameters: Seed: 76506 | Scale: 7.5 | Steps: 25 | Img Width: 512 | Img Height: 512 | model_version: 1.5fp16, trigger sentence: “fantasy landscape photography by Saudkova”).

Figure 17: Image generated on a laptop with DiffusionBee (parameters: Seed: 58862 | Scale: 7.5 | Steps: 25 | Img Width: 512 | Img Height: 512 | model_version: 1.5fp16, trigger sentence: “cute otter, disney pixar, detailed fur, lot of details”)

Figure 18: the reinforcement technique with simulation in the loop allow to learn and adapt with minimum numbers of real data (from [46], also explained on [47])

Figure 19: Nvidia Omniverse [49]

Figure 20: Low luminosity image improvement from [51]

Figure 21: Various trade-off due to quantization, according to CEA [53]

For example, having simulation in the loop, as shown by the Google research paper [46], allows a robot to learn to play table tennis against a human with minimal training; it can also generalize to play with other humans.

For the development of applications using deep learning, the user still has to provide a large database of data to train the networks (if using supervised learning approach). This can be solved by creating datasets through simulation in a life-like environment. For example, NVIDIA's Omniverse environment allows the creation of a photorealistic environment to train and simulate AI models [48].

These virtual environments allow the validation of AI models that use smaller datasets or only “reward” functions, as in the case of reinforcement learning or self-supervised learning. Later, these AI models can be used at the edge (inference phase), e.g. in robots or autonomous vehicles.

Data fusion and sequences result in better performance

Deep learning has provided breakthroughs in analysing unstructured data such as images. The analysis of the environment can be improved by adding more information, e.g. a sequence of images or other modalities. For example, the paper [50] [51] shows how dark images can be improved thanks to a temporal sequence of images. Other systems, fusing different modalities (visual and Lidar, for example [52]), allow better accuracy without needing more accurate input data. This kind of fusion is used in autonomous vehicles for example.

Tools are required to squeeze high-performing approaches into embedded systems

The key to implementing DNN into embedded devices, with limited resources, is being able to “simplify” the network, without degrading the performance (too much). This can be achieved either by pruning the topology of the networks, and/or by reducing the number of bits where weight and neuron values are stored. This technique, known as “quantization” is progressing quite rapidly, mainly driven

by the TinyML community. There are now many tools and libraries for reducing the size of DNN (including CEA's N2D2 [53], TensorFlow Lite [54], microTVM [55], NNOM [56] and TinyMaix [57], among others).

Developing approaches to reduce both the memory footprint and the computing power of algorithms for artificial intelligence required for inference and learning should be a priority for Europe. This would allow the mapping of complex applications onto edge devices, using AI. Europe should also support the development of innovative architectures that can be used in conjunction with the best of such reduced-size AI algorithms.

Why Europe should be a leader in embedded AI

The interfaces between the physical world and computing systems are key for the next generation of systems, like the “next web”, ambient intelligence, autonomous systems, etc. Consumers increasingly expect more natural interfaces with systems, such as voice. For reasons of privacy, latency and energy efficiency, processing often need to be performed locally, “at the edge” to avoid transferring data.

Europe has the potential to be a leader in these kinds of low-power but high-performance edge systems: Europe has a track record in embedded processing and systems (for applications in automotive, industrial automotive, transportation, etc) and has good researchers and engineers. Challenges of real time, safety, security and the sustainability of embedded systems should trigger research so that these properties are also expressed in AI technology; see [58], for example. However, Chinese and American companies are already in the race, and are developing integrated circuits (ICs) for edge applications. Europe should promote companies and start-ups in this field, and should develop tools to translate/map complex DDN into embedded chips (using pruning, quantization, etc...).

Europe should also promote the development of algorithms and systems supporting hybrid approaches that fuse different

modalities and kinds of AI (DNN and approaches which rely on explicit knowledge). European assets are its people, its variety (in term of spoken languages) and its use cases in the edge domain (automotive, industrial automation, healthcare and biomedicine, for example). Another application area where European edge-AI technology has potential is in space; the European Space Agency Earth-observation satellite ϕ -sat-1, for example, included technologies contributed from different European companies, while its chips had been radiation tested at CERN. Its images will be used to contribute to the Destination Earth digital twin initiative [59].

European systems (both those developed in and deployed in Europe) should follow European ethics and laws. European researchers should be at the forefront of translating new innovation in artificial intelligence for edge devices, and should bear in mind that today's megamodels will be in tomorrow's embedded systems.

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